

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF CORD-REINFORCED RUBBER COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The mechanical behavior of cord-reinforced rubber composite structure under tension, bending and torsion was investigated using a three-dimensional (3D) beam finite element method. The extension-twisting coupling due to the twisted nature of the cords as well as the coupled extension, bending, and twisting deformations characteristic cord-rubber composite structures were included in the finite element model. The accuracy of the present approach is demonstrated by comparing the results of coupled stiffness obtained from the finite element analysis to the available experimental data in the literature. The effect of cord orientation on the relative deformation/stiffness under tension, bending and torsion is presented to illustrate the effects of coupled behavior of cord-reinforced rubber composite structures.

KEYWORDS: finite element model, belt structure, stiffness couplings, twisted cord, rubber, structural analysis and design

INTRODUCTION

Cord-reinforced rubber composite structures with $\pm\alpha$ cord orientations find applications in automotive and aerospace engineering industries. The mechanical behavior of cord-reinforced rubber composite materials is generally complex due to the nonlinear geometric and material properties, and exhibit coupled axial-bending-twisting behavior under different loading conditions. The complexity of cord construction (as the cord itself is not a single filament but many filaments twisted together) results in the cords exhibiting coupled extension-twisting coupling behavior. It is important to include the coupled axial-bending-twisting behavior for the realistic analysis of cord-rubber composite structures and also to develop analysis techniques to design durable cord-reinforced rubber composite structures.

Several authors analytically investigated the response of cord-rubber composite laminates subjected to different loading conditions [1-8]. An exact expression for torsional stiffness of a single cord-rubber ply was developed by Bert and Chang [1] using St. Venant torsion theory. Akasaka et al. [2,3] studied the coupled extensional-torsional and bending-shear deformations of cord-rubber structures subjected to extension and bending. The torsional behavior of cord-rubber belt structures was studied by Akasaka et al. [4] including the interply shear deformation and torsional-extensional deformations. Robbins and Clark [5] presented an engineering analysis of bending stiffness of cord-rubber laminates based on laminate theory. They did not consider the interlaminar shear or coupled bending shear deformations. Bert [6] presented a theoretical treatment to predict the out-of-plane bending stiffness of a laminated composite plate under cylindrical bending based on classical lamination theory. Shield and

Costello [7] studied the extension-twisting coupling behavior of single-ply and two-ply cord-rubber composites using an energy approach based on the Ritz method.

It was experimentally shown by Turner and Ford [9] that significant interply shear strains exist when a two-ply composite structure is subjected to simple tension. These interply shear strains are believed to be mainly responsible for fatigue induced delamination in cord-rubber composite structures. Finite element analysis of cord-rubber composites was studied by many investigators [10-17]. Ford, Patel and Turner [10] have applied the axisymmetric finite element method to Turner and Ford's model of cord-rubber composites. Hsieh [11] and Cembrola and Dudek [12] presented finite element models for studying the behavior of cord-rubber laminates. De Eskinazi et al. [13] compared the results of interply shear strains from 2D and 3D finite element analysis and showed that the results were significantly different when 3D analysis was used. Pidaparti and Kakarla [14] presented a three-dimensional finite element model to study the non-linear extensional behavior of two-ply cord-rubber composite laminates. Later, they extended their study to analyze the three-dimensional torsional behavior of cord-rubber laminates [15]. The results indicated that coupled bending-shear and twisting shear deformations are important for a realistic analysis of the behavior of two-ply cord-rubber composite structures. Recently, bending analysis of two-ply cord-rubber composites and twisted cords was studied by Pidaparti using a hierarchical finite element approach [16].

In this study, a belt structure made from a cord-reinforced rubber composite and subjected to tension, bending and torsion was investigated using a recently developed three-dimensional beam finite element [16]. The extension-twisting coupling due to the twisted nature of the cords as well as the coupled extension, bending, and twisting deformations of cord-rubber composites was included in the finite element model. The accuracy of the present approach is demonstrated by comparing the results of coupled stiffness obtained from the finite element analysis to the available experimental data in the literature. The effect of cord orientation on the relative deformation/stiffness under tension, bending and torsion are presented to illustrate the effects of coupled behavior of cord-rubber composite structures. The three-dimensional finite element model presented would help in better understanding the mechanical behavior of cord-rubber composite structures under combined loading conditions.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Figure 1 shows the finite element modeling of a two-ply cord-rubber composite structure. The finite element model treats a two-ply composite composed of three layers through the thickness: two cord-rubber layers and a rubber layer as shown in Figure 1.

A recently developed finite element model [16] was used in this study. The present finite element model consists of a beam element and a warping element. The beam element is a three-node isoparametric finite element whereas the warping element is an eight node isoparametric element. The cross-section of the laminate consisting of cord-rubber and rubber layers was modeled using 8-node isoparametric finite elements (see Fig. 1). The finite element has beam nodes and warping nodes. Each beam node has three translational degrees of freedom and three rotational degrees of freedom (dof), respectively. Each warping node has a single dof in the beam direction but is normal to the deformed cross-section. The finite element model takes into account stiffness couplings due to axial, bending, twisting and warping deformations. The details of this beam/warping element can be found in Refs. [16,

17]. The present 3D beam element is computationally inexpensive as compared to the 3D solid finite element model.

Fig. 1. Finite element modeling of two-ply cord-rubber composite structure

The stress-strain relationships for the rubber and cord-rubber materials are assumed to be linear isotropic and linear orthotropic, respectively. The rubber elasticity is defined in terms of Young's modulus (E_m) and Poisson's ratio (ν_m). It is important consider the extension-twisting coupling behavior of twisted cords in the material model for a realistic analysis of cord-rubber composite structures. Shield and Costello [7] developed a material model for a unidirectional lamina of cord-rubber composite by assuming it to be monocyclic and taking into account the twisted nature of the cords. Their material model was derived from an energy approach and the Shield-Costello equations for a unidirectional cord-rubber composite are given by:

$$E_1 = E_m + c_1 E_c v_c \left[1 - \frac{6c_2 c_3 v_c (1 + \nu_m)}{c_1 (\bar{A} \bar{h}^2 \bar{E} + 6c_4 v_c (1 + \nu_m))} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$E_2 = \frac{4E_m [c_1 E_c v_c + E_m] + \frac{24(1 + \nu_m) v_c E_c}{\bar{A} \bar{h}^2} (c_4 E_m + C E_c v_c)}{[4E_m + 4(1 - \nu_m^2) v_c c_1 E_c] + \frac{24(1 + \nu_m) v_c}{\bar{A} \bar{h}^2 \bar{E}} (c_4 E_m + C E_c v_c (1 - \nu_m^2))} \quad (2)$$

$$G_{12} = G_m (1 - v_c) \quad (3)$$

$$\nu_{12} = \nu_m$$

where ν_m is the Poisson's ratio of rubber material, $\bar{A} = A_c / R^2$, $\bar{h} = h / R$, $\bar{E} = E_m / E_c$, A_c is the area of the cord, h is the thickness of cord-rubber ply, R is the outer radius of the cord and v_c is the cord volume fraction. The cord properties are described by Young's modulus of cord (E_c) and Poisson's ratio (ν_c). The constants c_1 , c_2 , c_3 , c_4 and $c = c_1 c_4 - c_2 c_3$ are used to describe the extension-twisting coupling and are determined analytically by Shield and Costello [7]. These constants depend on the helix angle of the cord and the ratio of inner wire

diameter to outer wire diameter. Recently, Shield and Costello applied this material model to study the mechanical behavior of single ply and two-ply cord rubber composite plates [7] and obtained good results. The above material model is included in the present finite element model.

Cord-rubber composites have different properties in tension and compression. In this study it is assumed that the properties in tension and compression are the same for all the cord-rubber elements. However, for a more realistic prediction, this bimodular properties [18] should be included in the present model. Linear static analysis is carried out to estimate the stiffness and relative deformations for a two-ply cord-reinforced rubber composite belt structure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A cord-rubber composite belt structure having $\pm\alpha$ cord orientation and subjected to tension, bending and torsion is considered. The geometry of the belt structure is 250 mm long, 63 mm wide and 3.7 mm thick as shown in Figure 2. The cord-rubber layers have a thickness of 1.45 mm and the rubber layer has a thickness of 0.8 mm. Since most composite belt structures have cord orientations of 10° to 40° to achieve best performance, these orientations were considered for finite element analysis.

Fig. 2. Geometry, loading and dimensions for a two-ply cord-rubber composite belt structure

The following material properties were used for the finite element analysis and were obtained from Refs. 4 and 5.

Rubber Properties:

$$E_m = 18.4 \text{ Mpa and } \nu_m = 0.5.$$

Steel cord geometric and material properties:

$$E_c = 184.0 \text{ GPa and } \nu_c = 0.3.$$

$$\text{Number of yarns} = 5, d = 0.25 \text{ mm}, d^* = 0.213 \text{ mm}, \text{ and } R_j = 0.088 \text{ mm}.$$

$$t_{piyarn} = 5, t_{picord} = 3, \text{ helix angle} = 81.4^\circ, \text{ and } \nu_c = 0.2976.$$

The constants for twisted cords $c_1=0.967$, $c_2=0.0828$, $c_3=0.187$ and $c_4=0.0723$ were taken from Ref. [7].

After conducting a convergence study, the two-ply steel cord-rubber belt structure was modeled using four beam elements (along the length) and twenty 8-noded elements over the cross-section. Coupled strain ratio which is defined as the coupled torsional-extensional deformation and torsional-bending deformation, generally present in angle-ply composites, was calculated from the finite element analysis. In order to validate the present finite element model the results obtained were compared to the experimental data for torsional loading and four-point bending for different cord orientations.

Figure 3 shows the variation of axial and torsional stiffness with cord orientation. It can be seen that the axial stiffness decreases as the cord-orientation is increased, whereas, the torsional stiffness increases as the cord-orientation is increased. The torsional stiffness is almost 3.8 times higher than the corresponding axial stiffness for a 20 degree cord orientation. However, this increase in torsional stiffness as compared to the axial stiffness increases when the cord orientation is increased. The bending stiffness variation with cord orientation is shown in Fig. 4. The bending stiffness decreases upto a cord-orientation of 15 degrees, increases up to a cord-orientation of 25 degrees and changes after that. It can be seen from Figs. 3 and 4 that tire belt stiffness is strongly dependent on the cord-orientation.

The coupled axial-twist deformation variation with cord-orientation is shown in Fig. 5 for both axial tension and torsional loading. It can be seen that the coupled deformation is higher for axial tension as compared to the torsional load. The coupled axial-twist deformation under axial load is almost 5 times higher than the corresponding coupled axial-twist deformation under torsional load for a 20 degree cord orientation. However, this increase in coupled axial-twist deformation under axial load as compared to the torsional load increases when the cord orientation is increased. The results presented in Fig. 5 illustrates the coupling effects under different loading conditions. Therefore, it is important to capture these coupled deformations for a realistic analysis of cord-rubber composite structures.

The results of coupled deformations and stiffnesses obtained from the present finite element analysis were compared to the experimental data for validation. Figure 6 shows the comparison of coupled torsional-extension deformations for different cord orientations under torsional loading. It can be seen that the present finite element results are in reasonably good agreement with the experimental data [4]. The results of bending stiffness for cord orientations of 15 to 30 degrees under four-point bending for the two-ply cord-rubber composite structure are compared to the results obtained from the present finite element analysis [16] in Fig. 7. It can be seen that a good agreement is found between the present finite element results and the experimental data [5]. The bending stiffness decreases as the cord orientation is increased. Good agreement of the above results validates the utility of the present finite element model for the analysis of cord rubber composites subjected to different loading conditions.

Fig. 3: Axial and torsional stiffness variation with cord-orientation

Fig. 4: Bending stiffness variation with cord-orientation

Fig. 5: Ratio of axial deformation to the twist variation with cord-orientation under tension and torsion.

Fig. 6: Comparison of coupled torsional-extensional strain for different cord orientations under torsion.

Fig. 7: Comparison of bending stiffness variation with cord orientation for a two-ply steel reinforced rubber structure.

CONCLUSIONS

The structural response of a cord-rubber composite belt structure subjected to axial tension, bending and torsional loading was investigated using three-dimensional beam finite element analysis. The present 3D beam element takes into account the coupled extension, bending, and twisting deformations as well as the twisted nature of the cords. The accuracy of the present model is demonstrated by comparing the results for torsional and bending loadings to the existing experimental data. The results presented indicate that cord orientation has a strong effect on coupled strain ratios. The results presented indicate the usefulness and applicability of the present finite element model to analyze cord-rubber composite structures under complex loading conditions.

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